

PACIFICUS

A LITERARY MAGAZINE

Print: 3082-4060
Online: 3082-4079

VOLUME 1

ISSUE 4 | OCTOBER - DECEMBER ISSUE
A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Creative Corner
- Others

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume I, Issue IV | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

DR. ARNOLD P. CANDAY

Assistant Professor IV

JH Cerilles State College

arnold.canday@jhsc.edu.ph

“I AM FINE”

(The Hidden Language of Stressed, Anxious and Depressed)

I carry myself like I'm okay—
head high, voice steady,
but inside, I'm unraveling.
I'm tired in ways sleep can't fix.

I try, I really do,
but it feels like I'm always falling short.
It's always me who reaches out,
who holds things together,
even when I'm breaking.

And still, I say it:
“I'm fine. Don't worry.”

Thoughts echo louder at night.
I joke around,
but my mind drifts to places I don't speak of.
I wear confidence like a uniform—
something I take off when no one's looking.

I've mastered the art of pretending,
because saying “I'm not okay”
feels like too much.

So I say it again:
“I'm fine. Don't worry.”

I don't want to be a burden.
I don't want to explain the weight I carry.
So I swallow the ache,
let silence speak for me.

Hope flickers,
but some days it barely glows.

I move through the fog,
slow, quiet, hollow.
And when they ask,

I smile and say it once more:
"I'm fine. Don't worry."

Because it's easier than saying
"I'm scared,"
"I'm tired,"
"I'm hurting."
So I keep the peace,
keep the mask,
keep the lie.
- "I am fine."

